

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D6.2 Dissemination & Communication Plans and Activities v2.0

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G-IA	5G Infrastructure Association
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EuCNC	European Conference on Networks and Communications
GA	Grant Agreement
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU-T	International Telecommunication Union - Telecommunication Sector
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MWC	Mobile World Congress
NGMN	Next Generation Mobile Networks
PO	Project Officer
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
RTOs	Research and Technology Organisations
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

D6.2 is an update of the previously submitted deliverable D6.1. It lists all the dissemination and communication activities carried out by the consortium to date (M26, October 2022).

The aim of the initial deliverable (D6.1) was to identify the target audiences, ranging from general public through scientific and academic communities up to specific 5G stakeholders and market actors; to define the dissemination and communication channels and actions; to show the dissemination and communication strategy divided in four phases; to present a complete dissemination and communication plan per partner and to explain the dissemination and communication guidelines for a successful internal organization.

D6.2 presents a detailed list of dissemination outputs:

- Scientific publications and white papers,
 - Conference papers
 - Journals/Magazines
 - Conference demonstrations
 - 5G-PPP white papers
 - 5G-PPP Brochure
- Conferences and workshops organization
 - Conferences/Forums organized by 5G-ROUTES partners
 - Special sessions organized in conferences
 - Workshops organization
- Training activities
 - PhD Schools organization
 - Tutorials organization
- Industrial exhibitions
- Interactions with worldwide fora and initiatives
- Other dissemination activities

And a detailed list of communication outputs:

- Online presence
- Press Releases and Success Stories
- Brochures/flyers
- Social Media
- Videos
- Newsletters
- Project meetings

At the end of the document Table 7 summarizes the dissemination and communication metrics and their corresponding target values.

D6.3 will show the progress at the end of the project (M48) detailing all the dissemination and communication activities carried out by all partners during the project.

2 Introduction

5G-ROUTES is a 5G-PPP Phase 3 project whose aim is to validate through robust evidence the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications (R.16 & R.17) of CAM under realistic conditions. In particular, it will conduct advanced large-scale field trials of most representative CAM applications to demonstrate seamless functionality across a prominent 5G cross-border corridor (Via Baltica-North), traversing Latvia, Estonia and Finland. This will help to boost confidence and accelerate the deployment of 5G-based interoperable CAM ecosystems and services throughout Europe. It also aims at validating 5G as a true enabler of innovative CAM services that cannot be realized by today's technology. Specifically, 5G-ROUTES will provide as specified in [1] :

- a) Validation of >150 network, business and service-level KPIs for 13 diverse CAM use cases that require 5G performance capabilities, covering several V2X scenarios in automated cooperative, awareness and sensing driving. 5G-ROUTES also focuses on uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go and multimodal services in the context of complete connectivity-enabled ecosystems around passengers and cargo over 3 different modes of transport (vehicles, rails and maritime)
- b) Innovative AI-based technological enablers for facilitating the execution of the field trials. Several scenarios will be considered for each use case covering cross-border, cross-telecom operators, cross telco-vendors, integrated cross terrestrial-satellite and cross-transport-mode settings. These will be incrementally validated, starting from lab trials, followed by localized large-scale trials at strategic cross-border locations (Valga city, Tallinn & Gulf of Finland) and finally in larger-scale trials covering significant portions of transport routes along the selected corridor.

The technical contributions of 5G-ROUTES are, without a doubt, the main priority of the project. However, the dissemination of the developed ideas and the obtained results to a wider audience, ranging from the research community to non-scientific public, is critical for the overall success and the impact of the project on society. WP6 aims to increase the visibility of 5G-ROUTES by coordinating the activities related to the dissemination of the results and the communication of the proposed solutions. To that end, a set of tools have been developed to promote the 5G-ROUTES solutions both to the expert and non-expert audiences.

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed (see Table 1).

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES Task		Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
Task 6.1 - Dissemination and communication activities	<i>Implement the dissemination of the project goals, software products, reports, results, achievements, and other outputs. The target audiences will be identified, ranging from general public through scientific and academic communities up to specific 5G stakeholders and market actors. The dissemination and communication channels and actions will serve as a baseline to achieve the goals in this task.</i>	Sections 6 and 8	The target audience and objectives for the dissemination and communication activities have been identified, along with the respective channels.
	Dissemination of publications and white papers: <i>Along the project, the 5G-ROUTES partners will be involved in the preparation and publication of articles in scientific journals, peer-reviewed conferences, and books. The approved publications will be available in the internal document repository of the consortium, and those with appropriate copyright permissions will be publicly available through the project's website.</i>	Section 7	This section lists all the publications generated by the consortium partners.
	Joint dissemination actions and events: <i>The project's intermediate results will also be presented in form of white papers, presentations and online demos in various conferences and industrial exhibitions with the purpose of commercially exploiting 5G-ROUTES results and identifying new partners for collaboration in the EU market. To further amplify the potential of the initiative, the following options will be considered: (i) joint organisation with other relevant 5G-PPP projects, (ii) co-hosting in the framework of other well-established events, (iii) organisation of a session with other 5G stakeholders, (iv) cooperation with 5G-PPP WGs and mapping of results.</i>	Sections 7 and 9	These sections show the dissemination and communication activities carried up to date.

	<p>Communication media: Ensure the creation and constant update of all web-based communication means, including the project's website (from M01 by EBOS). Participants will also ensure visibility of the project activities through a number of traditional and electronic dissemination material edited electronically and sent out to a large pool of stakeholders on a quarterly basis. Implement the communication plan of the project and its associated activities. Relevant activities include: (i) create and publish visual representations of information, data or knowledge intended to present complex information quickly and clearly; (ii) provide effective support to dissemination and exploitation activities, whilst ensuring effective and appropriate communication towards various stakeholders, (iii) foster community building and realise impact on industry and research in Europe and worldwide, (iv) gather feedback from relevant stakeholders through networking activities, and (v) monitor/evaluate communication and dissemination activities.</p>	Section 9	The website was created during the first month of the project. It is an ongoing task.
	<p>Development of the communication plan: Development of the communication plan, which will incorporate innovative methods for sharing information with the public and interested stakeholders.</p>	Sections 3, 4 and 8.	The dissemination and communication phases were defined at the beginning of the project (D6.1)
	<p>Tutorials & PhD schools: Organisation of 3 tutorials under the framework of important IEEE conferences and 2 PhD schools to inspire students to become the future generation of innovative and creative communication and networking researchers.</p>	Subsection 7.3	The section lists the activities related to tutorials and PhD Schools carried out so far.

WP6 5G-ROUTES Deliverables

D6.1: Dissemination & Communication plans and activities v1.0

Initial report containing the dissemination and communication plans and activities implemented.

D6.2: Dissemination & Communication plans and activities v2.0

Interim report containing the dissemination and communication plans and activities implemented.

D6.3: Dissemination & Communication plans and activities final version

Final report containing the dissemination and communication plans and activities implemented.

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The structure of the deliverable is as follows.

- Section 3 outlines how the project will establish and organise the dissemination actions to promote the project.
- Section 4 lists the dissemination activities carried out so far.
- Section 5 provides an outline of the target audiences of the communication strategy and their interest in 5G-ROUTES.
- Section 6 lists the communication activities carried out to date.
- Section 7 lists the metrics of interest and the targets for these activities.
- Finally, Section 8 includes the conclusions and next actions for this task.

2.3 Linkage to Other Project Outputs

This section shows the interdependencies of this deliverable with other deliverables, see Table 2.

Table 2: Interdependencies between deliverables

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	Deliverable Chapter(s)	Contribution and Value of linkage
INPUTS from other deliverables utilised in this report		
D6.4 Project Website and Social Media Presence [2]	Sections 3 (Project's Website) and section 4 (Project's Social Media Channels)	D6.4 Sections 3 and 4 introduces the website of the project and the social media channels which are referenced in this deliverable (Sections 8 and 9)
D6.1 Dissemination & Communication plans and activities v1.0	All sections	D6.1 is the initial version of this deliverable
OUTPUTS from this report utilised by other deliverables		
No outputs utilised by other deliverables		

3 Dissemination Activities

This section outlines how the project establishes and organises the dissemination actions to promote the project and the adoption of its outcomes beyond its lifetime.

3.1 Target Audience and Objectives

The general objective of the joint 5G-ROUTES dissemination strategy is to disclose project results that can be used by specific target audiences to progress their own work, i.e., to build upon the knowledge generated by 5G-ROUTES, fertilising the advancement of technology, science, industry and policy. 5G-ROUTES has identified several target audiences (see Table 3). The specific joint dissemination activities will be tailored to the needs and profile of the target audience.

Table 3: Target audience groups for dissemination

Target audience	Description	Dissemination Objectives
Academia & RTOs	Institutions primarily for education and early research for expanding their academic skills	To consider the results in updated curricula, advanced courses and new R&I initiatives
Public R&I	Institutions with innovation-oriented R&D and technology transfer (e.g., EU Investment Bank, Start-Up Europe, EC Digital Innovation Hubs)	To adopt the results in technology transfer and new R&I initiatives with industry
Government	Governmental agencies and authorities mainly concerned with policy setting (e.g., road traffic, railway traffic, port traffic authorities)	To consider the results in policy and new regulatory developments for CAM
IT experts from SMEs	Developers of new applications creating strong links with academia, RTOs and leading industrial entities, creating a strong value chain	To adopt the results for developing new innovative CAM applications, and to create strong links with industry and academia
Public/Private associations	Initiatives that leverage public and private resources and funds for joint undertakings (e.g., 5G-PPP, EIT Digital, European Private Equity)	To consider the results in the planning of joint public and private undertakings
Vehicle OEMs	Integrate intelligence and 5G communication components in vehicles for enabling CAM services	To adopt project's results in vehicles and in the planning of new features
Industrial equipment vendors	Private companies that maintain R&I groups for new product and services, e.g., telecom vendors, tier-1/tier-2 suppliers, vertical stakeholders	To adopt the results in product and service roadmaps, plan new products, services and future R&I initiatives
Telecom infrastructure providers and MNOs	The potential offered by innovative CAM services enables telecom providers to expand their service offerings, thereby increasing market share and growth rate.	To enhance and upgrade their existing telecom and mobile infrastructure to enable the offering of CAM services with guaranteed SLAs.

3.2 Dissemination Channels

A major element for dissemination relates to the joint and coordinated participation in relevant activities of the 5G-PPP[3] and the 5G Infrastructure Association (5G-IA). 5G-ROUTES will contribute to the brochures and other material coordinated at 5G-PPP level, such as the “*European 5G Annual Journal*”[4], the 5G-PPP projects brochure[5] and other material including videos[6], as requested by the 5G-IA and/or the Full5G CSA of the 5G-PPP. Furthermore, 5G-ROUTES has identified channels for the dissemination of the project’s results to scientific, technology and industry communities and specific activities which will be tailored to the needs, clients and events that will be used. More specifically, the target audience and the dissemination channels will be actively monitored and selected to achieve the highest possible impact in geographic areas relative to the partners’ own planned activities. Table 4 provides an outline of the target audience and channels.

Table 4: Dissemination channels and activities

Target audience	Channels
Universities, RTOs, Industry through International conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEEE GLOBECOM, IEEE International Conference on Communications 2021-2024, IEEE 5G Summit 2021-2024, ITS World Congress, Journal of Rail Transport Planning & Management, International Conference on Smart Transportation and Future Mobility, EUCAD 2021-2024, etc.
Universities, RTOs, Industry through scientific journals and magazines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), Elsevier Vehicular Communications, IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine, Springer journals, IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communication, IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine, IEEE Communications Magazine, etc.
Universities, RTOs, Industry, Public authorities through Dedicated Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of a focused group workshop by M27 to analyse the responses from questionnaires and surveys from the end-users of the CAM vertical sector providers (i.e., automotive, railways, transport & logistics, infotainment) so as to provide technical, business, security, privacy, policy and regulatory recommendations on the provision of cross-border CAM services. Organisation of two scientific workshops, open to academic and industrial communities, to present the intermediate and the final results, which will be co-located with important conferences. The 1st workshop will be organised by CERTH and VED by M25 (June 2022 at EuCNC/Global5G), and the 2nd by IQU and CTTC by M33 (Feb 2023 at MWC).
Universities, RTOs, Industry, Public/Private associations through the 5G-PPP and other 5G CAM initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution of project’s results to the 5G-PPP through its Work Groups, including participation to the dedicated monthly calls with other 5G-PPP projects to align the overall dissemination efforts. Interactions with worldwide fora and initiatives, e.g., 5G-AA, CAR2CAR Communication Consortium, ERTICO (where AIRBUS, VTT, VED and CERTH are active members), International Union of Railways, EU Rail Infrastructure Managers, etc., for the effective dissemination of project results and cross-fertilisation of ideas and concepts.

<p>Government, Industry, IT experts through Industrial Exhibitions, Business Conferences and Trade Fairs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobile World Congress-MWC-(2021-2024): Present results and activities related to the project’s use-cases to generate an ecosystem for 5G CAM validation closely related to the MWC. Members of the consortium will participate in the annual MWC events (e.g., ADS, ATOS, CTTC, EEE, TTU, VTT) and present innovations inspired from 5G-ROUTES. • EUCNC, Global 5G events, Connected Automated Driving (2021-2024): Present demos of use cases and results. BRA will showcase project outcomes at IBC (Amsterdam) and NAB (Las Vegas) broadcasting trade fairs.
<p>Universities, RTOs through Academic dissemination</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination to the academic community, of key results for use in teaching and training programs, for the preparation of educational material for technical schools and universities, detailed presentations and guidebooks for professionals. On-line project presentations on 5G-ROUTES scientific topics publicly available through the project’s website. Organisation of 3 tutorials under the framework of important IEEE conferences listed above and 2 PhD schools by CTTC to inspire M.Sc. and Ph.D. students to become the next generation of EU communication and networking researchers.

4 Dissemination outputs

The following subsections describe the dissemination actions carried out during the project lifetime.

4.1 Scientific publications and white papers

All the publications listed below have been updated on the SyGMA platform of the EC Participant Portal.

4.1.1 Conference papers

1. Laadung, T; Ulp, S.; Alam, M. M.; Le Moullec, Y. "**Active-Passive Two-Way Ranging Using UWB**", 14th International Conference on Signal Processing and Communication Systems (ICSPCS 2020), 14-16 December 2020, Adelaide, Australia. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/6555987>, 28 downloads (31/05/23).
2. Mwakwata, C. B.; Elgarhy, O.; Le Moullec, Y.; Alam, M. M.; Päränd, S.; Annus, I., "**Inter-cell Interference Reduction Scheme for Uplink Transmission in NB-IoT Systems**", 17th International Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC 2021), June 28 - July 2, 2021, Harbin, China, online. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/6556032>, 37 downloads (31/05/23).
3. M. Efthymiopoulou, K. Ramantas, N. Vesselinova, M. Mahtab Alam, L. Sanabria-Russo, C. Verikoukis. "**Multi-Domain Architecture for CAM Service Delivery Across Borders**", In IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (IEEE MeditCom) - Special Session: "AI Assisted Technologies for Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM)", 7-10 September 2021, Athens, Greece. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/6344799>, 87 downloads (31/05/23).
4. Mürsepp, I.; Kulmar, M.; Osama, E; Alam, M.M.; Chen T.; Horsmanheimo S.; Scholliers, J., "**Performance Evaluation of 5G-NR Positioning Accuracy Using Time Difference of Arrival Method**", IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking - MeditCom 2021, 7-10 September 2021, Athens, Greece. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/6556057>, 312 downloads (31/05/23).
5. M. Kulmar, I. Muursepp, M. M. Alam, "**The Impact of RAN Slice Bandwidth Subpartitioning on Slice Performance**", International Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC) 2022, 30 May - 3 June 2022, Dubrovnik, Croatia. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/6997838>, 36 downloads (31/05/23).
6. J. Baranda, J. Mangues-Bafalluy, L. Vettori, R. Martínez, E. Zeydan, "**Enabling the SLA Management of Federated Network Services through Scaling Operations**", 27th IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC 2022), 30th June - 3rd July 2022, Rhodes, Greece. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/7333186>, 21 downloads (31/05/23).
7. A. Mpatziakas, A. Sinanis, I. Hamlatzis, A. Drosou, D. Tzovaras, "**AI-Based mechanism for the Predictive Resource Allocation of V2X related Network Services**", 18th International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM 2022), 31 October - 4 November 2022, Thessaloniki, Greece. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/7956904>, 6 downloads (31/05/23).
8. H.W. Zaglauer, A. Lindenbergs, M. Lankinen, K. Körbe Kaare, K. Kuhi, M. Payaro, "**Providing Continuous 5G Connectivity along Ferry Lines – Concepts and Trials of 5G-ROUTES Project**", Invited paper, 2022 IEEE

Future Networks World Forum, 12-14 October 2022, Montreal, Canada. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/7984592>, 4 downloads (31/05/23)

4.1.2 Journals/Magazines

1. M. Maule, J.Vardakas and Ch.Verikoukis "**5G RAN slicing: dynamic single tenant radio resource orchestration for eMBB traffic within a multi-slice scenario**", in IEEE Communications Magazine, Vol.59, Issue 3, pp.110-116, March 2021. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/6346773>
 - Impact Factor: 9,03 – Quartile Q1
 - Zenodo downloads (31/05/23): 107
2. S. Z. Khan, M. M. Alam, Y. Le Moullec, A. Kuusik, S. Päränd and C. Verikoukis, "**An Empirical Modelling for the Baseline Energy Consumption of an NB-IoT Radio Transceiver**," in IEEE Internet of Things Journal, April 2021. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/6555624>
 - Impact Factor: 10,23 – Quartile Q1
 - Zenodo downloads (31/05/23): 28
3. C. B. Mwakwata, O. Elgarhy, M.M. Alam, Y. Le Moullec, S. Päränd, K. Trichias, K. Ramantas, "**Cooperative Scheduler to Enhance Massive Connectivity in 5G and Beyond by Minimizing Interference in OMA and NOMA**," in IEEE Systems Journal, October 2021. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/6555770>
 - Impact Factor: 4,80 – Quartile Q1
 - Zenodo downloads (31/05/23): 79
4. Laadung, T.; Ulp, S.; Alam, M. M.; Le Moullec, Y. "**Novel Active-Passive Two-Way Ranging Protocols for UWB Positioning Systems**", in IEEE Sensors Journal, November 2021. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/6555963>
 - Impact Factor: 4,32 – Quartile Q1
 - Zenodo downloads (31/05/23): 70
5. Anestis Dalgkitis; Luis A. Garrido; Farhad Rezazadeh; Hatim Chergui; Kostas Ramantas; John S. Vardakas; Christos Verikoukis, "**SCH2MA: Scalable, Energy-Aware, Multidomain Orchestration for Beyond-5G URLLC Service**", in IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems, September 2022. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/7875988>
 - Impact Factor: 9,55 – Quartile Q1
 - Zenodo downloads (31/05/23): 12
6. D. Rizopoulos, M. Laskari, G. Kouloumbis, I. Fergadiotou, P. Durkin, K. Kõrbe Kaare, M. M. Alam "**5G as an enabler for Connected-and-Automated Mobility in European Cross-border corridors – A market assessment**", in MDPI Sustainability Journal, October 2022. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/7308250>
 - Impact Factor: 3,88 – Quartile Q2
 - Zenodo downloads (31/05/23): 9

4.1.3 Conference demonstrations

1. J. Baranda et al. "**Demo: Automated Multi-Site E2E Orchestration of Hybrid Network Services Mixing PNF, VNF and CNFs**", 27th IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC 2022), 30th June - 3rd July 2022, Rhodes Island, Greece, virtual. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/7333211>. YouTube link: <https://youtu.be/8qlf3nAEt1Y>

Figure 1: Demo presentation at IEEE ISCC 2022

2. J. Baranda et al. **“ZSM-based Orchestration for Inter-Administrative Domain Cross-Border Vehicular Scenarios”**, IEEE International Conference on Sensing, Communication, and Networking (IEEE SECON 2022), 20-23 September 2022, virtual. Open access link: <https://zenodo.org/record/7341444>

4.1.4 5G-PPP white papers

1. **“Beyond 5G/6G KPIs and Target Values”**, 5G-PPP White Paper, Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation Working Group (TMW WG), TTU, June 2022. Link: <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-white-paper-beyond-5g-6g-kpis-and-target-values/>
 - Zenodo link: <https://zenodo.org/record/6577506>, 1896 downloads (26/5/2023)
2. **“From 5G to 6G Vision – A Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) perspective”**, 5G-PPP White Paper, 6G IA 5G for CAM Working Group, WINGS, CTTC, June 2022. Link: https://5g-ppp.eu/white-paper-from-the-6g-ia-5g-for-cam-wg-working-group-from-5g-to-6g_vision/
 - Zenodo link: not available

4.1.5 5G-PPP Brochure

1. ATOS, **“5GPPP Trials and pilots for connected and automated mobility C-V2X”**, 5G-PPP Brochure, May 2021. Link: https://5g-ppp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/5GPPP_TRIALS-AND-PILOTS-FOR-CONNECTED-AND-AUTOMATED-MOBILITY_C-V2X_brochure_Final.pdf

Figure 2: Mention of 5G-ROUTES in the 5G-PPP brochure

4.2 Conferences and workshops organization

This section summarizes the events organized during the project so far.

4.2.1 Conferences/Forums organized by 5G-ROUTES partners

1. LMT was strategic partner in the organization of the **5G Techritory 2020 - Europe's Leading 5G Ecosystem Forum** and participated in the panel **Mobility session - How safe mobility will develop through advances of mobile connectivity and AI**, Riga, Latvia, 11-12 November 2020. Link: <https://www.5gtechritory.com/5g-techritory-2020/>

13:00 - 13:45
OMEGA STAGE

HOW SAFE MOBILITY WILL DEVELOP THROUGH ADVANCES OF MOBILE CONNECTIVITY AND AI

The meaning of people-oriented mobility lies in having a safe, convenient, and reliable access to going to work, school, and other destinations daily, be it by public transport, private car, bicycle, or on foot. Is that today's reality, something from the near future, or just a distant dream? This panel discussion will guide us through today's main insights from technology deployment, legislation, and overall readiness for safe mobility.

Moderator:
 Caspar de Jonge
PROGRAM MANAGER DATA AND SERVICES

Participants:

- Arturs Lindenbergs
INNOVATION LEAD, HEAD OF MOBILITY INNOVATIONS, LMT
- Ilkka Kotilainen
SPECIAL ADVISER, Finnish Transport and Communications Agency (Traficom)
- Peter Stuckmann
HEAD OF UNIT – FUTURE CONNECTIVITY SYSTEMS - DIRECTORATE-GENERAL FOR COMMUNICATIONS NETWORKS, CONTENT AND TECHNOLOGY (DG CONNECT), European Commission
- Dmitry Konyagin
ENTERPRISE BUSINESS TEAM LEADER, NVIDIA

Figure 3: 5G Techritory 2020 Forum – Panel participation

2. CTTC organized the **IEEE international Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking 2021** (MeditCom2021), 7-10 September 2021, Athens, Greece. Link: <https://meditcom2021.ieee-meditcom.org/>

IEEE.org | IEEE Xplore Digital Library | IEEE Standards | IEEE Spectrum | More Sites

IEEE ComSoc
IEEE Communications Society

IEEE

IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking

7-10 September 2021 // Hybrid: In-Person and Virtual Conference

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Figure 4: IEEE MEDITCOM 2021 conference

- LMT was strategic partner in the organization of the **5G Techritory 2021 - Europe's Leading 5G Ecosystem Forum** and participated in the panel **5G Routes - Future of mobility**, 22-25 November 2021. Link: <https://www.5gtechritory.com/agenda/>

Figure 5: 5G Techritory 2020 Forum – Panel participation

- TTU organized the **Baltic Electronics Conference (BEC) 2022** conference co-sponsored¹ by 5G-ROUTES, 4-6 October 2022, Tallinn, Estonia. Link: <https://taltech.ee/en/bec2022>

Figure 6: BEC 2022 conference

4.2.2 Special sessions organized in conferences.

- CTTC, IQU and TTU organized in collaboration with ICT4CART (<https://ict4cart.eu/>) and 5GCroCo (<https://5gcroco.eu>) projects the **AI Assisted Technologies for Connected and Automated Mobility Special Session (AI for CAM SS)**, IEEE MeditCom 2021, 7-10 September 2021, Athens, Greece. Link: https://meditcom2021.ieee-meditcom.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/159/2021/03/SS2_AIforCAM_5GROUTES-ICT4CART-5GCroCo_Meditcom_2021_Special_Session.pdf

¹ 5G-ROUTES funding supported the technical service needed for the remote participation of some of the speakers

IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking
5-8 July 2021 // Athens, Greece

Special Session
AI Assisted Technologies for Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM)

Organizing Projects	5G-ROUTES (https://www.5g-routes.eu/) ICT4CART (https://ict4cart.eu/) 5GCroCo (https://5gcroco.eu/)
Structure	2 h, 1 Keynote speaker, 5 papers
Organizers	Natalia Vesselinova, CTTC, natalia.vassileva@cttc.es Maria Efthymiopoulou, Iquadrat, mefthymiop@iquadrat.com Muhammad Mahtab Alam, TAlTECH, muhammad.alam@taltech.ee Vasilis Sourias, ICCS-NTUA, v.sourias@iccs.gr

Background and Motivation

The European Commission's goal is to make the mobility of people and goods in the EU safer, cleaner, more efficient, more accessible, and more user-friendly. The 5G networks are expected to contribute to the realization of this ambitious vision through innovative *Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM)* applications. However, connected vehicles and especially connected autonomous driving vehicles bring a whole new ecosystem with demanding requirements such as high throughput and latency below 1 ms. Furthermore, CAM applications need to seamlessly function throughout all terrains (including dense cities, remote rural areas and maritime paths) and when crossing borders. The delivery of CAM services should be independent of the mode of transport too and regardless of whether passengers or cargo are involved. Network slicing (for providing differentiated service), distributed Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC for enabling innovative services by bringing the network capacity and intelligence to the edge) together with the potential of AI (powered by the vast amounts of network data and context-aware data generated by vehicle sensors and roadside units) are the key enablers for realizing the CAM vision. In this call we seek contributions that can support the workloads and satisfy the real-time service requirements of the connected and autonomous driving vehicles through holistic, AI-assisted MEC, network slicing, vehicular positioning and spectrum use solutions.

Figure 7: IEEE MeditCom 2021 5G-ROUTES Special Session

4.2.3 Workshops organization

1. Stella Nikolaou (CERTH), **“Internal Workshop for Business Criteria Weighting”**, 11th March 2022, online. Internal 5G-ROUTES workshop with requested attendance by all partners and experts from all project competences.

5GROUTES
5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

CERTH
CENTRE FOR RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY HELLAS

T5.2 Impact Assessment & CBA
Business Criteria Weighting Workshop
March 11, 2022

Stella Nikolaou, CERTH
snikola@cERTH.gr

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 961867

T5.2 Impact assessment and cost/benefit analysis

Impact assessment and cost/benefit analysis of dedicated and validated 5G architecture and CAM

- to justify commercially the technologies and the deployment investments, whilst addressing the social and environmental impact.

Use the results gained from the field trials

- to credibly deliver a validated results-based cost/benefit analysis for the wide deployment of 5G CAM infrastructure along major routes in Latvia, Estonia and Finland.

Consolidated and verified description of new business opportunities

- based on the qualitative and quantitative market assessments of 5G-ROUTES use cases and the collaboration with the business modelling activities, perform a consolidated expert-based multi-criteria analysis of the new market opportunities on 5G CAM.

Figure 8: T5.2 internal workshop by CERTH

2. EEE, LMT, VEDIA, TELIA, CERTH, ILS, **“Seamless connectivity over the sea and on harbours”**, Business Workshop, 5G Techritory Conference, 29th November 2022, Riga, Latvia. This event focuses on investigating the business perspective of maritime technological developments within the 5G-ROUTES project, the results of which will be scaled and implemented at-large. Participation of 30 external stakeholders stemming mainly from the maritime sector. Link: <https://www.5gtechritory.com/seamless-connectivity/>

Figure 9: 5G Techritory Business workshop

4.3 Training activities

4.3.1 PhD Schools organization

CTTC and TTU organized in collaboration with 5GCroCo (<https://5gcroco.eu>) project the **“Summer School on 5G Connected Automated Mobility across Europe”**, 1st Summer School on challenges and technologies for a 5G Connected Automated Mobility across Europe, 23-24 May 2022, EURECOM Sophia-Antipolis, France. Link: <https://5g-x-eu.eurecom.fr/>

Figure 10: Projects presentation (professionals)

Attendance: 63 people (20 doctoral students). 18 people attended the event in person while 45 did so remotely.

The Opening Keynote talk was given by the Project Officer, Jorge Pereira. BRA, CERTH, TTU, SWA, VTT, VED, EDI and EBOS from 5G-ROUTES consortium participated with technical talks. Finally, a student poster session was held to close the PhD School.

Figure 11: Poster session (PhD students)

Figure 12 and Figure 13 show the program of the PhD School.

Time	Monday May 23 rd	Tuesday May 24 th
9:00-9:10	Welcome Address J. Härrri (EURECOM/5GCroCo) Yannick Le Moullec (TalTec/5G-ROUTES)	
09:10 – 10:00	Opening Keynote – Jorge Pereira, European Commission (EC)	Technical Session 3 5G enabled VR applications (BRAINSTORM MULTIMEDIA SL) Online multi user AR game – Javier Montesa – “Online VR conference” – Andrea Castelli
10:00 – 10:15	Coffee Break	Coffee Break
10:15 – 11:15	5GCroCo & 5G-ROUTES Project Introduction Miquel Payaro (Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya – CTTC) – Kati Kõrbe (Ericsson Estonia)	Technical Session 4 “Application of Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence methods to enable Vehicle related 5G Services” – Asterios Mpatziakas (CERTH) and Anastasis Sinanis (CERTH), in collaboration with Anastasios Drosou (CERTH) – Mobile positioning in 5G networks – Ivo Muursepp (TTU)
11:15– 11:30	Coffee Break	Coffee Break
11:30-12:30	Technical Session 1 Implementing Automated Mobility Use Cases in a Cross-Border Environment Using 5G Infrastructure José Rodriguez (Swarco), in collaboration with Johan Scholliers (VTT), Pierre Merdrignac (VEDECOM), and Oskars Teikmanis (EDI) – 5G-Routes Tenant Web Portal – Collection and visualisation of Use Case trial data, measurements and KPIs Sozos Karageorgiou and Christos Skoufis (EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED – EBOS)	Technical Session 5 Feedback from FOT – Trials for tangible results – Theory and practice Maciej Muehleisen (Ericsson, Germany)

Figure 12: PhD School program (I)

12:30 – 13:30	LUNCH	LUNCH
	<p>Virtual Poster Session</p> <p>5G mobile connectivity for Intelligent Transport Systems</p> <p>–</p> <p>The impact of RAN slice bandwidth subpartitioning on slice performance: UE clustering</p> <p>–</p> <p>In-Person Poster Session</p> <p>Hybrid GNSS-5G Vehicular Localization in Urban Environments</p> <p>–</p> <p>Effect of Road-Induced Vibrations and Antenna Position on Beam-Based Vehicular Communications</p> <p>–</p> <p>Scheduling in Radio Resource Coordination and Management for 5G and Beyond Massive Connectivity</p> <p>–</p> <p>Spatial-Interference Aware Cooperative Resource Allocation for 5G V2V Communications</p> <p>–</p> <p>A Geoservice CPM based Object Detection Service for CCAM</p> <p>–</p> <p>Optimal Data Rate for 5G NR Sidelink in V2X communication</p>	<p>Technical Sessions 6</p> <p>QoS Prediction for Automated Driving Apostolos Kousaridas (Huawei, Germany)</p> <p>–</p> <p>5G Backend Cross-border Challenges Soumya Datta (EURECOM), in collaboration with Orange, Stellantis, Groupe Renault and CCTC</p> <p>–</p> <p>Tele-Operated Driving – Achievements of the ToD Use Case In 5GCroco Andreas Schimpe (Technische Universität München – TUM) and Andreas Pfadler (VW, Germany)</p>
13:30 – 15:00		
15:00– 15:15	Coffee Break	Coffee Break
	<p>Technical Session 2</p> <p>Docker Security for 5G deployment & FOT Fabian Würfl (SecConsult, Austria)</p>	<p>Closing Session</p> <p>Open Floor Discussion on Vision towards 6G Jérôme Härrı (EURECOM) & Yannick Le Moullec (TalTec)</p> <p>–</p> <p>Farewell</p>
15:15 – 16:15		
16:15 – 17:00		EURECOM Open5G Lab tour (optional)
20:00	Social Dinner / activity	

Figure 13: PhD School program (II)

4.3.2 Tutorials organization

1. Pat O'Sullivan (ILS) organized an internal tutorial titled **“5G-ROUTES: focused patent education session”**, 26 November 2021, online.
2. TTU organized the tutorial **“5G-ROUTES: 5G for CAM Across Cross-Border Corridors”** as part of the Baltic Electronics Conference (BEC) 2022, 4 October 2022, Tallinn, Estonia.

Agenda - Talks:

- Plenary Invited Speaker Dr. Jorge Pereira - Principal Scientific Officer, European Commission, Title: **“TEN-T corridors within the CEF digital program”**.
- **“ZSM-based Orchestration for Inter-Administrative Domain Scenarios”**, Jordi Baranda - Catalan Telecommunications Technology Centre (CTTC), Spain.
- **“5G Radio Coverage Analysis for Cross-border Context”**, Priit Roosipuu, Tallinn University of Technology (TTU), Estonia
- **“Enabler for the exchange of V2X messages in 5G networks”**, Anastasia Yastrebova – VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd., Finland.
- **“Cooperative Automated Vehicle Control and 5G”**, Artis Rušņņš and Oskars Teikmanis – Elektronikas un Datorzinātņu institūts (EDI), Latvia.

Figure 14: 5G-ROUTES tutorial at the BEC 2022 conference

4.4 Industrial exhibitions

1. IQU participated with a booth in the **Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2021**, June 28 - July 1, 2021, Barcelona, Spain, <https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/mwc-2021>
 - The exhibition had an attendance of 20.000 people (industry and academy). An average of 20 people per day visited the booth.
2. SWARCO participated with a booth in the **ITS World Congress 2021**, 11-15 October 2021, Hamburg, Germany, <https://itsworldcongress.com>
 - The Congress had 15.000 registrations. Several experts visited SWARCO’s booth to find out about the 5G-ROUTES project.

Figure 15: SWARCO at the ITS World Congress 2021

Figure 16: CTTC at the MWC 2022

3. LMT participated in the **GITEX Technology week 2021**, 17-21 October 2021, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, <https://gitex.com/show-highlights/>
 - More than 5.000 exhibitors, 800 startups and over 100.000 attendees.
4. IQU and CTTC participated with 2 booths in the **Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2022**, 28th February – 3rd March 2022, Barcelona, Spain. Link: <https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/mwc-2022>
 - 61.000 total attendees from 184 countries and territories
 - Both stands had an average of more than 25 visits per day.
5. LMT participated with a booth in the **Intertraffic 2022**, 29th March – 1st April 2022, Amsterdam, Netherlands. Link: <https://company.intertraffic.com/LMT--Latvijas-Mobilais-Telefons-?Language=EN&eventid=38111&account=00619046-0>
 - More than 23.500 attendees from 121 countries worldwide
 - Our booth was visited by more than 20 experts every day.

Figure 17: LMT at the Intertraffic 2022

Figure 18: BRA at the NAB SHOW 2022

6. BRA participated with a booth in the **National Association of Broadcasters (NAB) SHOW 2022**, 23-27 April 2022, Las Vegas, United States. Link: https://nab22.mapyourshow.com/8_0/exhibitor/exhibitor-details.cfm?ExhID=132
 - Total registered attendees: 52.468 from 155 countries.
 - 5G-ROUTES booth was visited for more than 30 people, on average, every day.
7. CTTC participated as exhibitor in the **IOT Solutions World Congress (IOTSWC) 2022**, 10-12 May 2022, Barcelona, Spain. Link: <https://www.iotsworldcongress.com/>
 - Around 12.000 attendees
 - An average of 10 people every day visited our booth interested in 5G-ROUTES.

Figure 19: CTC at the IOTSWC 2022

8. SWARCO participated in the **14th ITS European Congress 2022**, 30 May – 1 June 2022, Toulouse, France. Link: <https://itseuropeancongress.com/>
 - The congress gathered more than 6.500 delegates from more than 60 countries.
9. 5G-ROUTES shared a booth with ICT-53 5GMED (<https://5gmed.eu/>) and 5G-BLUEPRINT (<https://www.5gblueprint.eu/>) projects in the **European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC) and the 6G Summit 2022**, 7-10 June 2022, Grenoble, France. EEE represented the project at the booth. Link: <https://www.eucnc.eu/>
 - Overall registrations: 584 in-person, 80 remote. Total: 664 people
 - More than 30 companies visited our booth.

Figure 20: 5G-ROUTES booth at EUCNC 2022

10. BRA participated with a booth in the **International Broadcasting Convention (IBC) 2022**, 9-12 September 2022, Amsterdam, Netherlands. Link: <https://show.ibc.org/>
 - More than 37.000 attendees from over 170 countries.
 - The booth was visited by 20 people/companies per day.

4.5 Interactions with worldwide fora and initiatives

#	Partner involved	Type of Activity	Name of activity	Dissemination Action	Date	Place	Number/types of participants	Link
1	LMT	Networking event	Interactions with 5G Automotive Association (5GAA)	LMT presented 5G-ROUTES project and virtual cross-border deployments to all 5GAA partners	20 October 2021	Virtual	5GAA partners	N/A
2	CERTH	Networking event	HUMANIST Virtual Network of Excellence - Meeting	- Project presentation to the HUMANIST VCE Board CERTH is a Board Member of the HUMANIST Virtual Centre of Excellence	27 October 2021	Rhodes, Greece	European (10 members)	https://www.humanist-vce.eu/
3	VEDIA	Networking event	CaaS Nordic and ITS Estonia association	2-day seminar/workshop about digital logistics	3-4 May 2022	Tallinn, Estonia	35 participants from Finland, Estonia and Lithuania	https://twitter.com/CaaS_Nordic/status/1521411732173897728?s=20&t=1GIZ0sbtpH1pa4zODKNK3g
4	LMT	Networking event	5G Automotive Association	LMT presented 5G-ROUTES project and virtual cross-border deployments to all 5GAA partners	20 October 2021	Virtual	5GAA partners	https://twitter.com/5gRoutes/status/1549403571120218112?s=20

4.6 Other activities

#	Partner involved	Type of Activity	Name of activity	Dissemination Action	Date	Place	Number/types of participants	Link
1	TTU	Workshop participation	5G Techritory 2020 - Europe's Leading 5G Ecosystem Forum.	- Panel Discussion "Security through supply chain diversification"	11-12 November 2020	Riga, Latvia (Hybrid event)	2053 participants from 107 countries.	https://www.5gtechritory.com/updates2020/agenda
2	EEE, TELIA, TTU	Communication	Research in Estonia	Research in Estonia under Estonian research council organized an interview with Ericsson Estonia, Telia Estonia and TTU "With 5G-Routes, Estonian Scientists, Industry Partners Strive for Regional Interoperability"	December 2020	Estonia	National level	https://researchinestonia.eu/2020/12/09/with-5g-routes-estonian-scientists-industry-partners-strive-for-regional-interoperability/

#	Partner involved	Type of Activity	Name of activity	Dissemination Action	Date	Place	Number/type s of participants	Link
3	EEE	Conference participation	IEEE 5G Virtual Summit - IEEE 5G for CAM	5G-ROUTES general presentation	11-12 May 2021	Brussels, Belgium	International participation of several CAM projects with about 100 participants	http://5gsummit.org/CAM/
4	CTTC, IQU, ATOS, WINGS, CERTH, EBOS, VTT, TTU	Background Conference paper	IEEE 5G for CAM Summit 2021	"The 5G Route to Connected and Automated Mobility: the 5G-ROUTES Project"	11-12 May 2021	Brussels, Belgium	International participation of several CAM projects with about 100 participants	http://5gsummit.org/CAM/ https://5g-mobix.com/assets/files/The-5G-Route-to-Connected-and-Automated-Mobility-the-5G-ROUTES-Project.pdf
5	EDI	Talk	"EDI Day" Event	Introduction to 5G-routes talk	19 May 2021	Latvia	Around 40 attendees	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5DSSkU1yApc (from 42:02 till 48:00)
6	WINGS	Participation in Special Session – extended abstract - Talk	2021 IEEE MeditCom - Special Session: AI Assisted Technologies for Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM)	"Slice Negotiator and Service Continuity in X-Border Environment" extended abstract talk.	7-10 September 2021	Athens Greece (Hybrid event)	Around 25 attendees	https://zenodo.org/record/6345094#.Yi92tZbOFhF https://meditcom2021.ieee-meditcom.org/
7	ADS	Presentation at Invited Colloquium - Talk	38th International Communications Satellite Systems Conference (ICSSC)	Presentation "5G Satellite Connectivity for CAM" containing dissemination of 5G-Routes scope and objectives	27 September 2021	Washington DC, US (Virtual event)	About 100 attendees during the presentation	https://www.kaconf.com/doc/program.pdf
8	ENIDE	Talk	Semana de la Carretera 2021	Disseminate objectives and first results of the project	11 November 2021	Madrid, Spain	More than 40 experts	https://31semanadelacarretera.aecarretera.com/
9	LMT	Talk	5G Techritory 2021, 4th Europe's leading 5G ecosystem forum	"5G-Routes - future of mobility" talk	22-25 November 2021	Riga, Latvia	International	https://www.5gtechritory.com/5g-techritory-2021/

#	Partner involved	Type of Activity	Name of activity	Dissemination Action	Date	Place	Number/type of participants	Link
10	WINGS	Talk	Infocom World 2021	"Advanced Enablers and Applications for Cooperative and Automated Mobile Cross-border Environments" talk	24-26 November 2021	Athens Greece	Around 25 attendees	https://infocomworld.gr/
11	SWARCO	Newsletter	TTS Italia - Project of the month - 5G-ROUTES Project	Participation in national newsletter	14 December 2021	Italy	National level	https://www.ttsitalia.it/newsletter/13_dicembre_2021.html#progettomesedue
12	WINGS, IQU	Workshop participation	FITCE Technology Forum	Participation in "Round Table: Challenges of 5G technology" in Session III: Advancements in connected and automated mobility	17 December 2021	Athens Greece (Hybrid event)	Around 100 attendees	https://www.fitce.gr/5o-fitce-technology-forum/ https://www.fitce.gr/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/FITCE-Workshop-Agenda.pdf
13	EDI	Talk	Talk about 5G-ROUTES	Doctoral seminar at University of Latvia	23 February 2022	Latvia	+20 attendees	N/A
14	WINGS	Open Call for SMEs	1st Open Call for SMEs, start-ups and spin-offs for CAM testing	Announced on the website of the project, Social Networks and email.	Call dates: 15.03.2022-20.04.2022	-	International	https://www.5g-routes.eu/news-events/
15	VEDIA, VTT	Panel participation	Webinar: Traffic data quality criteria, indicators and applications	Participation in a panel of national webinar	17 March 2022	Finland	45 ITS related companies	N/A
16	SWARCO	Talk	Smart Mobility Congress at the Latin American level	Participation in an international congress	4-5 April 2022	Latin America (virtual)	+30 ITS related companies	https://www.linkedin.com/events/icomgresodemovilidadinteligente6901997564892459008/
17	EBOS	Workshop participation	"1st Open Annual Workshop on Future ICT" workshop	Presentation: "5G Technologies and Cybersecurity in EU H2020 Funded Projects"	25 May 2022	Athens, Greece	50 attendees	N/A

#	Partner involved	Type of Activity	Name of activity	Dissemination Action	Date	Place	Number/type s of participants	Link
18	SWARCO	Conference participation	28th International Conference on Urban and Maritime Transport and the Environment	An abstract was submitted to present 5G-Routes project as well as the synergies between use cases 2.1, 3.1, and 3.3.	19-21 September 2022	Valencia, Spain (Online)	International	https://www.wessex.ac.uk/conferences/2022/urban-and-maritime-transport-2022

5 Communication Activities

5.1 Target Audience and Objectives

The following Table 5 provides an outline of the target audiences of the communication strategy and their interest in 5G-ROUTES.

Table 5: Target audience groups for communication

Target Group	Description	Interest in the project
A - Industry, SMEs and Entrepreneurs	Stakeholders from industry, network operators, SMEs and entrepreneurs, operating in the 5G CAM domain (e.g., EU MNOs, OTT providers, 5G AA, 5G ACIA, CAR2CAR, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilisation of project's results in operations and in their R&I activities for new service and product development. Amplify innovation in 5G CAM by blending 5G-ROUTES results with in-house artefacts
B - 5G PPP infrastructure Programme Stakeholders	Participants, project partners and relevant stakeholders active in the 5G PPP Work Groups, other 5G-PPP projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of common topics Synergies and collaborations for results promotion Enhancing innovation through results combination Co-organisation of events
C – Technology Clusters	European initiatives and clusters, research communities, associations, (e.g., ETNO, NetWorld2020, Digital Business Innovation, Digital Agenda, Innovation Union, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusion of project's results to collaborative research activities (roadmap, white papers...) Dissemination of project's results to their members Participation in project's events for knowledge exchange
D – Researchers and Academics	Researchers and academics working in universities, research centres, R&I departments of industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advancing research post-project Training personnel and students Porting results to real-life industry cases
E – Policy Makers	Policy-makers at any level (e.g. Council of Regions, EC Directorate for Communication, European Radio Spectrum Policy Group)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluation of the project's techno-economic and regulatory aspects Definition of future research and innovation directions based on project's acquired knowledge
F – Standards bodies and fora	Standards bodies, industry fora, open-source organisations (e.g., 3GPP, ETSI, IETF, NGMN, IEEE, ITU-T, ISO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of roadmaps for standards development Input for standardisation activities
G – General Public	General public and anyone interested in the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the value of European research Stimulate innovation in unexpected groups of society

Based on the target audience groups identified above and their expected interest in the project, the objectives of the joint communication strategy and their relation to the target audience groups are identified in Table 6.

Table 6: Communication objectives

Objectives Description	Target groups						
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Provide a clear view of the project goals and its results, including the 5G-PPP perspective	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Create an active community of interested stakeholders and potential users and collect knowledge and requirements considered by the project's activities	●	●	●	●	●	●	
Prepare the ground for the exploitation of project's results towards the industry	●	●				●	
Create awareness of the project among the full range of stakeholders impacted by the results	●	●	●	●		●	
Establish liaisons with other projects and initiatives for knowledge and innovation transfer		●	●	●	●	●	

Support the dissemination and exploitation of results (including the 5G PPP programme results) by formulating adapted key messages, and prepare adapted communication material	●		●	●		●	
Recognition of the results (including the 5G-PPP programme results) among the research communities, standardisation bodies, potential users, policy-maker institutions.		●	●	●	●	●	

5.2 Communication Channels

The 5G-ROUTES communication strategy combines a mix of traditional and disruptive communication channels:

- **Online presence:** A project website was created in M01 and **maintained by EBOS** serving to i) promote the project's public image and serve as a main online access point for the different target groups; ii) serve as an information source, highlighting project objectives, activities, outcomes and relevant updates; iii) serve as a repository of information.
- **Press and TV/Radio Interviews:** 5G-ROUTES partners publish press releases in order to show major achievements and the potential of 5G as a future-proof technology for CAM services. The consortium attempts to reach the general audience via TV/radio interviews. 5G-ROUTES press releases should be revised and approved by LMT before publication. LMT will ensure that the press release is not biased and does not contain confidential information. **LMT is responsible for this activity.**
- **Brochures/flyers:** 5G-ROUTES will prepare technical brochures providing information about the technical and scientific achievements and non-technical brochures-factsheets describing the potential project applications and services in a more accessible manner. **CTTC supervises this activity.**
- **Social media:** 5G-ROUTES use several online social media sites (Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube), as a two-way access between the project partners and the technical and public audience. The consortium is regularly publishing announcements. **IQU is responsible for this activity.**
- **Video clips:** several video clips have been produced so far, covering the 5G-ROUTES general ideas, demonstrations, presentations and talks. **This activity is coordinated by CTTC.**
- **Newsletters:** The newsletters produced from the beginning of the project, available at the project's website, are providing information regarding the project activities, achievements and results. **CTTC is responsible for this activity.**

6 Communication outputs

6.1 Online presence

The initial page of the website is depicted in Figure 21. A detailed description and analysis of the project’s website is described in D6.4 “Project website and social media presence” which was submitted in M1 of the project.

Figure 21: 5G-ROUTES website

Figure 22: Statistics – Website overview

Figure 22 shows an overview of the website, more than 3500 users, almost 12.000 visits and an average of 200 visits per month are the most notable statistics. In addition, Figure 23 shows the ranking of the countries from which the website is most visited.

Figure 23: Statistics – Location analysis

6.2 Press Releases and Success Stories

The press releases and success stories listed below are related to the project. Some of the links lead to web pages in a language other than English since they are dissemination actions on the local public of each partner.

1. **“5G-ROUTES launch event”**, ENIDE website, ENIDE, September 2020, <https://www.enide.com/?p=1917>
2. **“5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials (5G-Routes)”**, EDI website, EDI, October 2020, <https://www.edi.lv/en/projects/5th-generation-connected-and-automated-mobility-cross-border-eu-trials-5g-routes/>
3. **“Unique 5G Solutions to be tested in Estonia”**, Tallinn University of Technology website, TTU, November 2020, <https://taltech.ee/en/news/unique-5g-solutions-be-tested-estonia>
 - Estonian version: <https://taltech.ee/uudised/telia-vedamisel-hakatakse-eestis-testima-seninagematuid-5g-lahendus>
4. **“With 5G-Routes, Estonian Scientists, Industry Partners Strive for Regional Interoperability”**, Research in Estonia website, EEE - Telia - TTU, December 2020, <https://researchinestonia.eu/2020/12/09/with-5g-routes-estonian-scientists-industry-partners-strive-for-regional-interoperability/>

5. **"5G- ROUTES 3rd plenary meeting"**, EDI website, EDI, January 2021, <https://www.edi.lv/en/on-january-11th-2021-the-5groutes-3rd-plenary-meeting-took-place/>
6. **"European Researchers Night 2021"**, EDI website, EDI, event in Latvian, April 2021, <https://www.edi.lv/30-aprili-edi-piedalises-zinatnieku-nakts-2021-tiessaistes-aktivitates/>
7. **"Urban Mobility Hackathon"**, Urban Mobility Hackathon event website, LMT, April 2021, <https://www.urbanmobility.io/public-events/breakfast-session>
8. **"EDI days 2021"**, EDI website, EDI, event in Latvian, May 2021, <https://www.edi.lv/edi-diena-tiessaiste-19-maija/>
9. **"LMT un CSDD Bīķernieku trasē izveidojis 5G testa trasi savienotajiem un bezpilota auto"**, LMT website, LMT, local press release in Latvian, August 2021, <https://www.lmt.lv/lv/preses-relizes?g=2021&pid=1076>
10. **"Bīķernieku trasē izveido 5G testa trasi savienotajiem un bezpilota auto"**, Dienas Bizness (DB) website, LMT, local press release in Latvian, August 2021, <https://www.db.lv/zinas/lmt-kapina-apgrozijumu-503699>
11. **"Bīķernieku trasē LMT un CSDD izveidojis 5G testa trasi bezpilota automašīnām"**, Delfi Auto website, LMT, local press release in Latvian, August 2021, <https://www.delfi.lv/auto/zinas/bikernieku-trase-lmt-un-csdd-izveidojis-5g-testa-trasi-bezpilota-automasinam.d?id=53520285>
12. **"Latvia launches first cross-border mobility simulation space"**, Smart Cities World website, LMT, September 2021, <https://www.smartcitiesworld.net/news/latvia-launches-first-cross-border-mobility-simulation-space-6887>

Figure 24: 5G-ROUTES Smart Cities World website press release

13. **“Latvia launches first cross-border mobility simulation space”**, Here4dbest website, LMT, September 2021, <https://here4dbest.com/latvia-launches-first-cross-border-mobility-simulation-space/>
14. **“Latvia's LMT starts cross-border 5G-Routes project”**, Telecompaper website, LMT, September 2021, <https://www.telecompaper.com/news/latvias-lmt-starts-cross-border-5g-routes-project--1396418>
15. **“What’s up with... OneWeb & AT&T, NEC & AWS, Telenor”**, Telecom TV website, LMT, September 2021, <https://www.telecomtv.com/content/access-evolution/what-s-up-with-oneweb-at-t-nec-aws-telenor-42337/>
16. **“LMT’s new 5G mobility testbed to become the first cross-border mobility simulation space in Europe”**, LMT Innovations website, September 2021, <https://innovations.lmt.lv/news/lmts-new-5g-mobility-testbed-to-become-the-first-cross-border-mobility-simulation-space-in-europe/>
17. **“Latvia launches first 5G cross-border test site in Europe”**, Developing Telecoms website, LMT, September 2021, <https://developingtelecoms.com/telecom-technology/enterprise-ecosystems/11862-latvia-launches-first-5g-cross-border-test-site-in-europe.html>
 - **“Latvia launches first 5G cross-border test site in Europe”**, Telecombizz website, LMT, link to the previous press release, September 2021, <http://telecombizz.com/latvia-launches-first-5g-cross-border-test-site-in-europe/>
18. **“Latvian Operator LMT Launches Cross-border 5G Mobility Testbed”**, The Fast Mode website, LMT, September 2021, <https://www.thefastmode.com/investments-and-expansions/20747-latvian-operator-lmt-launches-cross-border-5g-mobility-testbed>
 - **“Latvian Operator LMT Launches Cross-border 5G Mobility Testbed”**, The Fast Mode website, LMT, link to the previous press release, September 2021, <https://www.newsbreak.com/news/2369116393913/latvian-operator-lmt-launches-cross-border-5g-mobility-testbed>
19. **“Latvia launches cross-border mobility simulation space”**, Labs of Latvia website, LMT, September 2021, <https://labsoflatvia.com/en/news/latvia-launches-cross-border-mobility-simulation-space>
20. **“5G testbed enables mobility simulation space”**, ITS International website, LMT, September 2021, <https://www.itsinternational.com/its7/its8/news/5g-testbed-enables-mobility-simulation-space>
21. **“Cross-border connectivity and 5G”**, Intertraffic website, LMT, November 2021, <https://www.intertraffic.com/news/autonomous-driving/cross-border-connectivity-and-5g/>
22. **“Nākotnes mobilitāte: zinātniskā fantastika ir reālāka, nekā šķiet”**, Dienas Bizness (DB) website, LMT, local press release in Latvian, November 2021, <https://www.db.lv/zinas/nakotnes-mobilitate-zinatniska-fantastika-ir-realaka-neka-skiet-505289>
23. **“LMT shares the latest 5G-Routes project updates at the 5G Techritory Forum”**, LMT Innovations website, December 2021, <https://innovations.lmt.lv/news/lmt-shares-the-latest-5g-routes-project-updates-at-the-5g-techritory-forum/>
24. **“Valkā izmantos 5G tehnoloģijas satiksmes regulēšanai”**, Delfi Bizness website, LMT, local press release in Latvian, January 2022, <https://www.delfi.lv/bizness/tehnologijas/valka-izmantos-5g-tehnologijas-satiksmes-regulesanai.d?id=54004906>

Figure 25: 5G-ROUTES Intertraffic website press release

- 25. **"5G ROUTES transport and 5G"**, VEDIA website, VEDIA, March 2022, <https://www.vedia.fi/blog/5g-routes-transport-and-5g/>
- 26. **"Cross-border connectivity"**, Intertraffic World magazine, digital and hard copy, LMT, March 2022, <https://itw.mydigitalpublication.com/publicatiotn/?m=67195&i=732180&p=36&ver=html5>

Figure 26: 5G-ROUTES Intertraffic World magazine press release

27. **“5G Routes first open call”**, ENIDE website, ENIDE, March 2022, <https://www.enide.com/?p=2955>
28. **“Latvian 5G engineers played games on phone while driving lorries and using apps”**, Mobile Europe website, LMT, May 2022, <https://www.mobileeurope.co.uk/latvian-5g-engineers-played-games-on-phone-while-driving-lorries-and-using-apps/>
29. **“5G technology takes several steps forward in Latvia”**, ENG LSM, LMT, May 2022, <https://eng.lsm.lv/article/economy/business/5g-technology-takes-several-steps-forward-in-latvia.a457163/>
30. **“5G-ROUTES consortium members test first use cases in LMT’s 5G cross-border mobility testbed”**, LMT Innovations website, LMT, May 2022, <https://innovations.lmt.lv/news/5g-routes-consortium-members-test-first-use-cases-in-lmts-5g-cross-border-mobility-testbed/>
31. **“First 5G cross-border V2X tests completed in Latvia”**, Traffic Technology Today, LMT, May 2022, <https://www.trafficechnologytoday.com/news/connected-vehicles-infrastructure/video-first-5g-cross-border-v2x-tests-completed-in-latvia.html>
32. **“5G use cases demonstrated in cross-border mobility project”**, SmartCitiesWorld, LMT, May 2022, <https://www.smartcitiesworld.net/4g-and-5g/5g-use-cases-demonstrated-in-cross-border-mobility-project>

Figure 27: 5G-ROUTES SmartCitiesWorld website press release

33. **“Biķernieku trasē demonstrē 5G pārrobežu mobilitāti”**, Labs of Latvia website, LMT, local press release in Latvian, May 2022, <https://labsoflatvia.com/aktuali/5g-parrobezu-mobilitate>
34. **“LMT signs a memorandum with RBF to bring 5G connectivity and innovations to the maritime sector”**, LMT Innovations website, LMT, June 2022, <https://innovations.lmt.lv/news/lmt-signs-a-memorandum-with-rbf-to-bring-5g-connectivity-and-innovations-to-the-maritime-sector/>
35. **“LMT audzē apgrozījumu par 11,9%, turpina investīcijas 5G tīklā”**, Delfi Bizness website, LMT, local press release in Latvian, July 2022, <https://www.delfi.lv/bizness/tehnologijas/lmt-audze-apgrozijumu-par-11-9-turpina-investicijas-5g-tikla.d?id=54561708>
36. **“LMT apgrozījums aug par 11,9%”**, Labs of Latvia website, LMT, local press release in Latvian, July 2022, <https://labsoflatvia.com/aktuali/lmt-apgrozijums-aug-par-11>

6.3 Brochures/flyers

1. EBOS, **5G-ROUTES factsheet**, April 2021 (updated May 2022), <https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/5G-ROUTES-PROJECT-FACTSHEET.pdf>

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

About 5G-ROUTES Project
 5G-ROUTES is a 5G-PPP Phase 3 project whose aim is to validate through robust evidence the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications (R.16 & R.17) of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) under realistic conditions. In particular, 5G-ROUTES will conduct advanced large-scale field trials of most representative CAM applications to demonstrate seamless functionality across a prominent 5G cross-border corridor (Via Baltica-North), spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitised motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe.

Objectives

- 1 To develop innovative and commercially exploitable CAM UCs for automotive, railway and maritime sectors within the cross-border context.
- 2 To analyse the technical and business requirements for the UCs to enable extensive large-scale CAM field trials.
- 3 To advance and optimise the enabling technologies using AI for the reliable, seamless and uninterrupted delivery of interoperable CAM services across borders.
- 4 To develop the infrastructure, integrate the technological enablers in an E2E CAM ecosystem, setup the 5G corridor and facilitate lab and large-scale field trial validation.
- 5 To demonstrate the potential and the user value in advanced CAM deployments at cross-border areas.
- 6 To develop and validate the business models of advanced CAM UCs and protect EU IP.
- 7 To provide rationalised contribution to key standardisation bodies within the CAM context.
- 8 To ensure long-term success through wide dissemination of the project's results; to exploit synergies with other 5G-PPP projects and 5G CAM initiatives.

Horizon 2020 call & Topic: H2020 – ICT- 2020 / ICT-53-2020
Start date: September 1st, 2020 **Duration:** 48 months
Coordinator: ERICSSON EESTI AS
Consortium: 21 partners from 9 EU Countries
Total funding: € 9,177,397.88

CAM Trials & Cross-border Use Cases

UC Category 1: Automated Cooperative Driving
 UC1.1: Dynamic vehicles platooning
 UC1.2: Cooperative lane change
 UC1.3: See through view for safe automated overtake

UC Category 2: Awareness Driving
 UC2.1: Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control
 UC2.2: Traffic jam chauffeur

UC Category 3: Sensing Driving
 UC3.1: Sensor info sharing.
 UC3.2: Connected maintenance.
 UC3.3: Vulnerable Road User (VRU) collision avoidance

UC Category 4: Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go
 UC4.1: 360o Immersive multi-user gaming on the go
 UC4.2: 3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go

UC Category 5: Multimodal services
 UC5.1: Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics
 UC5.2: 5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight
 UC5.3: Future Railways Mobile Communication Systems (FRMCS) telemetry operation

Consortium

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 951867.

Figure 28: 5G-ROUTES Factsheet

2. EBOS, **5G-ROUTES Banner/roll-up**, April 2021 (updated May 2022), <https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/5g-routes-rollup-banner.pdf>

Instrument: ICT-53-2020
Start date: September 1st, 2020
Duration: 48 months
Total funding: € 9,177,397.88

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

5G-ROUTES is a 5G-PPP Phase 3 project whose aim is to validate through robust evidence the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications (R16 & R17) of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) under realistic conditions. In particular, 5G-ROUTES will conduct advanced large-scale field trials of most representative CAM applications to demonstrate seamless functionality across a prominent 5G cross-border corridor (Via Baltica-North), spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitised motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe.

OBJECTIVES

- 1**

To develop innovative and commercially exploitable CAM UCs for automotive, railway and maritime sectors within the cross-border context.
- 2**

To analyse the technical and business requirements for the UCs to enable extensive large-scale CAM field trials.
- 3**

To advance and optimise the enabling technologies using AI for the reliable, seamless and uninterrupted delivery of interoperable CAM services across borders.
- 4**

To develop the infrastructure, integrate the technological enablers in an E2E CAM ecosystem, setup the 5G corridor and facilitate lab and large-scale field trial validation.
- 5**

To demonstrate the potential and the user value in advanced CAM deployments at cross-border areas.
- 6**

To develop and validate the business models of advanced CAM UCs and protect EU IP.
- 7**

To provide rationalised contribution to key standardisation bodies within the CAM context.
- 8**

To ensure long-term success through wide dissemination of the project's results; to exploit synergies with other 5G-PPP projects and 5G CAM initiatives.

CONSORTIUM

Sg-routes.eu
 5G-ROUTES Project
 5G-ROUTES Project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 951867.

Figure 29: 5G-ROUTES roll-up

3. **Business Validation, Models, and Ecosystems Sub-Group (BVME) of the 6G-IA Vision and Societal Challenges Working Group Brochure**, June 2022, promotional Factsheet for the "IEEE GLOBAL COMMUNICATIONS CONFERENCE", 4–8 December 2022, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Figure 30: BVME brochure

6.4 Social Media

5G-ROUTES project has shared on social media events attended and relevant news. Two channels were created at the beginning of the project: **LinkedIn** (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/5g-routes-project/>) and **Twitter** (<https://twitter.com/5gRoutes>), which are shown in Figure 31 and Figure 32, respectively. Moreover, Figure 33 shows the 5G-ROUTES Youtube channel. At the time of writing this deliverable the LinkedIn account has 263 followers while the Twitter account has reached 239 followers.

D6.2 Dissemination & Communication plans and activities v2.0

Figure 31: 5G-ROUTES LinkedIn profile

Figure 32: 5G-ROUTES Twitter

Figure 33: 5G-ROUTES YouTube Channel

6.5 Videos

Several videos have been prepared to disseminate the 5G-ROUTES project. Below you will find the links to the different platforms that host the videos.

1. **“First use case – a teleoperated vehicle simulation conducted remotely over LMT’s 5G network”**, LMT, EDI, Latvian, August 2021, <https://www.facebook.com/LatvijasMobilaisTelefons/videos/361764912075022/>
2. **“Lepazīsti tehnoloģijas 2021: Atvērtā nodarbība #1 / Get to know technology 2021: Open online webinar #1”**, LMT, Latvian, August 2021, <https://www.facebook.com/LatvijasMobilaisTelefons/videos/569132800757741/>
3. **“TV3 episode “Technologies without instruction” - a teleoperated vehicle simulation conducted remotely over LMT’s 5G network”**, LMT, EDI, Latvian, September 2021, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Hv_qCKMeLY
4. 5G-ROUTES is briefly mentioned in a **video about the cooperation between Telia Estonia and Tallinn University of Technology** (from 2:00 to approximately 2:40), Estonian, TTU, TELIA, September 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=00HWaRxIb3A>
5. Video of the first use case where a teleoperated vehicle simulation was conducted remotely over 5G network **“5G mobility testbed”**, LMT, EDI, October 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=puRbAuNNUpM>

Figure 34: Screenshot of the 5G mobility testbed video

6. Video from 5G Techritory forum (Techflix stage) with a topic **"5G Routes- Future of Mobility"**, LMT, November 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oaUyjGz9-jM>

Figure 35: Screenshot of the 5G Techritory video

7. **TV24 episode "DigiTuvi" (Digitally close) - transport, mobility, transport, 5G ROUTES**, LMT, Latvian, December 2021, https://xtv.lv/rigatv24/video/AOGZr4xBG4Z-22_12_2021_digituvi_2_dala
8. **"CaaS Digital supply chain"**, the video describes how logistics events are formed in supply chains and how those can be recorded in digital format so that in the future this data could be shared among supply chain stakeholders, VEDIA, VTT, ENIDE, 19 January 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eG2E2G71dp0>
9. **"5G-ROUTES promotional video"**, All partners, led by LMT, May 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1jqDFqw6G8>

Figure 36: Screenshots from the 5G-ROUTES promotional video

10. **"First use cases in LMT's 5g cross-border mobility testbed"**, 5G-ROUTES demonstration of use-cases in Riga, LMT, May 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PPLmss8298I>
11. **"IBC 2022 Brainstorm demo full Day 1"**, 5G-ROUTES dissemination, minute 8:15, BRA, <https://vimeo.com/749921727>

6.6 Newsletters

5G-ROUTES has published 3 newsletters prepared by CTTC with the collaboration of all partners so far. Each 6 months the most important dissemination and communication activities are reported in these newsletters. All are accessible from the website of the project: <https://www.5g-routes.eu/dissemination-communication/newsletters/>

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials (951867)

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- Publications 2
- Conference organization 2
- Press releases 2
- White Papers 3
- Factsheet 3
- Kick-off meeting 4
- Deliverables 4
- Social media 4

Consortium

Newsletter
September 2020-June 2021
Issue Number 1

5G-ROUTES Project Overview

5G-ROUTES is a 5G-PPP Phase 3 project whose aim is to validate through robust evidence the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications (R.16 & R.17) of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) under realistic conditions. In particular, 5G-ROUTES will conduct advanced large-scale field trials of most representative CAM applications to demonstrate seamless functionality across a prominent 5G cross-border corridor (Via Baltica-North), spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitised motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe.

Objectives:

1. To develop innovative and commercially exploitable CAM UCs for automotive, railway and maritime sectors within the cross-border context.
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5. To demonstrate the potential and the user value in advanced CAM deployments at cross-border areas.
6. To develop and validate the business models of advanced CAM UCs and protect EU IP.
7. To provide rationalised contribution to key standardisation bodies within the CAM context.
8. To ensure long-term success through wide dissemination of the project's results; to exploit synergies with other 5G-PPP projects and 5G CAM initiatives.

Figure 37: 5G-ROUTES Newsletter #1

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- Conference organization 2
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- Exhibitions 3
- Press releases 4
- Videos 5
- Other activities 5
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- Social media 6

Consortium

Newsletter July-December 2021 Issue Number 2

5G-ROUTES Project Status

Dear reader,

On behalf of the 5G-ROUTES consortium, I am happy to introduce to you the second 5G-ROUTES newsletter, which provides information on our latest activities, publications and deliverables.

5G-ROUTES project focus is conducting advanced large-scale field trials of most representative CAM applications to demonstrate seamless 5G functionality across Via Baltica-North corridor to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitised shipways, railways and motorways throughout Europe. Our project has also been impacted by the instabilities of recent periods. 5G SA network availability in Baltic states, COVID-19 related restrictions and supply chain disruptions have all impacted the project timeline, resulting in 5G-ROUTES project extension of 12 months.

The project has made substantial technical progress over the first 18 months and fundamentals to conduct the project work have been set. In this newsletter you can find a short overview of the submitted deliverables, journal and conference publications, organized conferences and special sessions. 5G-ROUTES has also participated in different exhibitions and trade shows to stay in touch with the industry.

Finally, I'd like to invite you to connect with us via social media channels to stay updated about our progress.

Happy reading!

Kristjan Kuhl
5G-ROUTES coordinator

Figure 38: 5G-ROUTES Newsletter #2

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials (951867)

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Consortium

Newsletter
January-June 2022
Issue Number 3

Introduction

During the first half of 2022, the COVID-19 pandemic affected the development of the project to a lesser extent than in previous periods. Fortunately, the dissemination activity has not stopped and numerous actions and activities have been carried out to promote the project in both physical and virtual formats. Below we list those activities that can be found in more detail in this Newsletter:

- Publication of 2 conference papers
- Participation in 2 white papers of the 5G-PPP
- 1 demonstration in a conference
- 1 internal workshop was organized for the partners of the project
- 6 participations in international fairs
- Several links to press releases
- 3 videos related to the project have been published on YouTube
- 1 PhD school has been organized together with the 5GCroco project
- The “1st Open Call for SMEs, start-ups and spin-offs for CAM testing” has been organized
- Several talks have been given in workshops organized by third parties where the project has been promoted
- 2 plenary project meetings have been held
- 7 deliverables have been delivered
- Our activity on social networks has increased compared to previous periods

Enjoy reading!

David Pubill
Dissemination Manager

Figure 39: 5G-ROUTES Newsletter #3

6.7 Project meetings

Several consortium meetings have been held since the start of the project. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the meetings until October 2021 were all held virtually. Since then, they have been held in hybrid mode.

1. Kick-off Plenary meeting, 17-18 September 2020, virtual meeting.

Figure 40: Kick-off virtual meeting. September 2020.

2. 2nd General Assembly, 8 December 2020, virtual meeting
3. 3rd General Assembly, 11 January 2021, virtual meeting
4. 4th General Assembly, 29 April 2021, virtual meeting
5. 1st Review meeting, 17-18 June 2021, virtual meeting.
6. 5th General Assembly, 19-20 October 2021, Tallinn (Estonia), Hybrid meeting.

Figure 41: 5th General Assembly. October 2021.

7. 6th General Assembly, 16 March 2022, Tallinn (Estonia), Hybrid meeting.

Figure 42: 6th General Assembly. March 2022.

8. 2nd Review meeting, 12-13 May 2022, Riga (Latvia), Hybrid meeting.

Figure 43: 2nd Review Meeting. May 2022

9. 7th General Assembly, 14-15 September 2022, Tallinn (Estonia), Hybrid meeting.

Figure 44: 7th General Assembly. September 2022.

7 Metrics and Targets

Table 7 lists the dissemination and communication metrics and their corresponding target values. It shows the metrics at month M14 (when D6.1 was resubmitted) and at month M26 which corresponds to October 2022. The website of the project has been updated with the most relevant dissemination and communication activities (<https://www.5g-routes.eu/dissemination-communication/>).

Table 7: Dissemination and communication outcome, metrics and targets

Dissemination Activities				
Activity/Metrics	Description	Target value	D6.1 (M14)	Current value (M26)
Industrial exhibitions	Participation in exhibitions	>9	1	10
	Exhibition booths	>3	1	9
Scientific publications	Journals/magazines (+ white papers)	>9	2	8
	Conferences	>20	4	8
	Conference demonstrations	>6	0	2
	Conference/Forum organization or sponsorship	-	-	4
Workshops/surveys	Technical workshops organized	2	1	2
	Participants per technical workshop	>70	15	>70
	Focused group workshop surveys	1	0	0
	Participants per focused group	>100	0	0
	Talks, workshops attended, other activities	-	-	17
5G-PPP Programme	Number of WGs to contribute	7	7	7
	Interactions with fora/initiatives	>4	0	4
Training	Online tutorials	3	0	2
	Number of PhD schools	2	0	1
Online repository	Number of publicly available deliverables	>20	7	11
Communication Activities				
Activity/Metrics	Description	Target value	D6.1 (M14)	Current value (M26)
Project website	Online by	M1	Yes	Yes
	Unique visitors from M12	1000	>1000	>1000
	Unique visitors from M36	2000	-	-
Social media	LinkedIn group followers	>200	138	262
	Twitter followers	>200	116	239
	Tweets	>200	16	72
	Banners	>30	0	2
Press releases / Newsletters	Press releases	>5	22	36
	Newsletters	>6	1	3
Factsheets / Brochures	Technical factsheets	3	0	0
	Non-technical factsheets	3	1	2
	Hardcopies	>1000	250	250
Video clips	Number of online video clips	2	0	11
	Number of video views	>1000	-	>1000
Flyers / posters & roll-ups	Project flyers	>3	1	1
	Posters & roll-up banners	>3	1	1

Note: Cells in green mean that the objective has already been achieved.

So far, no Facebook profile has been created as we consider LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube social media channels today to be more professional than a Facebook one.

8 Conclusions and Next Actions

Deliverable D6.1 (M5) provided the initial dissemination and communication plan of the 5G-ROUTES project. Regarding the dissemination activities, we identified the target audience and the main dissemination channels that will be exploited during the project for the dissemination of the technical outcome and results. Regarding the communication activities, the target audience and stakeholders were identified, while the qualitative communication objectives were defined. In the same context, the most important communication channels (e.g., project's website, newsletters, event organization, etc.) were also listed.

This deliverable is an update of the previous one and collects all the dissemination and communication activities carried out to date (M26, October 2022). Thanks to the improvement regarding the covid-19 pandemic and the new focus of the project, the activities carried out have increased significantly. For example, it is worth noting the large number of fairs covered by the partners, most of them with a stand where the project has been promoted internationally. We have also participated in the organization of various conferences/forums that have given the project a lot of visibility. However, we still have some work to do in terms of publications, we expect to increase these numbers as the technical aspects of the project progress. Regarding training activities, we have organized a PhD School jointly with 5GCroco project and two tutorials, one in the framework of an IEEE conference and another one internal for the project partners. We are on the right track to achieve the expected target values. In communication we have increased our presence on Social Media networks, and we are very active in the publication of press releases in the Media. In addition, every 6 months a Newsletter is published with the most relevant dissemination and communication activities carried out during that period.

The objectives of the project have changed significantly compared to those initially proposed. We will adapt the dissemination activities to the new paradigms proposed, ensuring a good dissemination rather than complying with the initially proposed metrics. In this sense, we will analyze those activities that we have carried out up to now and we will assess which ones are more conducive to having a dissemination as international as possible. In turn, we will discard those that do not provide us with what we want. In this sense, we have already identified some fairs, such as the IOTSWC, which both in terms of subject matter and the experts that attend, strays a bit from the project's roadmap.

At the end of the project, deliverable D6.3 will provide the final report on dissemination and communication activities carried out throughout the project.

9 References

- [1] 5G-ROUTES Grant Agreement (number 951867)
- [2] D6.4 Project Website and Social Media Presence: https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Attachment_6.4.pdf
- [3] <https://5g-ppp.eu/>
- [4] 2020 edition at <https://bscw.5g-ppp.eu/pub/bscw.cgi/d356008/Full%20G%20Annual%20Journal%202020.pdf>
- [5] Current edition available at <https://5g-ppp.eu/flipper-brochure/>
- [6] Project videos at <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-phase-3-videos-now-available/>